

Study of Unnatural Deaths among Tea Garden Workers of Sonitpur District, Assam

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Received: 25-06-2024 / Revised: 23-07-2024 / Accepted: 25-08-2024

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Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:

Unnatural deaths among tea garden workers poses a serious challenge to the health authorities and brings forth socio economic differences to the fore. The present study aims to study the pattern of unnatural deaths among tea garden workers in Sonitpur district of Assam, India. A cross sectional retrospective study was done in cases brought for medicolegal autopsy to a tertiary medical college for a period of 3 years. A total of 248 cases were included in the study. Males constituted the highest number of cases. The age group of 21-30 years and 31-40 years were most commonly involved. Road traffic accidents (47.18%) and Suicides done by hanging (19.36%) were the leading cause of such deaths. Deaths occurred more in the months of October, December and January.

Keywords: Autopsy, Unnatural Death, Pattern, Suicide, Tea Garden.

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Introduction

Tea and the related industry are one of the most important industries for Assam which drives its economy and the most important cog in it are its workers. Sonitpur district in Assam has nearly 59 small and large tea gardens with nearly 2-2.5 lakh population. [1] Since ages these workers have been marginalized resulting in poor development of the community. With poor infrastructure, unique beliefs and nonexistent health capabilities the tea workers and their families lagged behind the general population in many aspects. But with renewed vigour and policies of both Central and State Government, health and disease treatment has shown an improvement over the years. In spite of such measures the number of unnatural deaths has shown no signs of receding and with improved communication capabilities reporting of such cases has only increased. The primary objective is to investigate the reasons to the unnatural deaths among tea garden workers and also the propensity for such deaths which is unknown. Studies to the various health determinants and natural diseases among tea workers highlight nutritional deficiencies, anemia, hypertension and the high intake of alcohol and tobacco but very few have data for the unnatural deaths among them. [2-5] Also the relevant practices among the workers which leads to more unnatural deaths is relatively unknown.

Methodology

A Cross Sectional Retrospective study was done on all cases belonging to workers of tea garden brought for medicolegal autopsy to a tertiary referral medical college in Sonitpur district of Assam, India for a time period collecting 3 years data from 1st July 2019 to 30th June 2022. Data sources are the autopsy reports, inquest reports and dead body challan available for the cases. Data was fed into a structured data entry form and kept in a coded form so that no personal or identifiable data shall be divulged during the course of study.

Statistical analysis of data was done by using Microsoft Excel and presented in tabular forms. All data was then compared with relevant literature available. Decomposed cases were excluded from the purview of the study.

Results

A total of 248 cases has been included in the study. This represents 21.42% of the total 1158 autopsies done during the study period. Males outnumber females in a ratio of 3:1 with 186 cases and 62 cases respectively

Table 1: Age distribution of cases according to sex

Age	Male	Female	Total	Percent
0-10	3	1	4	1.61
11-20	25	9	34	13.71
21-30	58	24	82	33.07
31-40	41	15	56	22.58
41-50	22	6	28	11.29
51-60	18	5	23	9.28
Above 60	19	2	21	8.46
Total	186	62	248	100

Highest number of cases were recorded in the age group of 21-30 years(33.07%) followed by 31-40 years (22.58%). Extremes of ages were less commonly involved. (Table 1)

Table 2: Showing distribution of cause of death

Cause of death	Number	Percent
Hanging	48	19.36
Burns	25	10.08
Poisoning	29	11.69
Road traffic accident	117	47.18
Drowning	6	2.42
Railway accident	1	0.41
Animal attack	8	3.22
Homicide	14	5.64
Total	424	100

Of these cases, the three leading causes of death were road traffic accidents (47.18%), followed by hanging (19.36%) and poisoning (11.69%). The fatal poisoning cases were due to consumption of poisons related to agriculture and farming (insecticides, rodenticides, weed killers and fungicides). Animal attack deaths and burns were notable inclusions as cause of death. (Table 2)

The manner of death was accidental in 132 cases(53.22%) followed by suicide involving 102 cases (41.13%). In both the age groups of 21-30

and 31-40 years accident was the leading manner of death. However in the cohort of 31-40 years both suicides and accidents were equal with 31 cases. Homicide was more common in the 31-40 years cohort .There were 14 cases of homicide out of which 9 involved sharp edged weapons and the rest blunt weapons. The principal method of suicide was hanging followed by poisoning. In poisoning 8 cases of alcohol poisoning were noted over the study period. There were both accidental and suicidal burns.(Table 3)

Table 3: Showing manner of death by age distribution

Age	Suicide	Accident	Homicide	Total
0-10	0	2	0	2
11-20	8	15	2	25
21-30	26	42	2	70
31-40	31	31	4	66
41-50	18	24	2	44
51-60	12	12	3	27
Above 60	7	6	1	14
Total	102	132	14	248

Monthly distribution of cases didn't show any significant changes. The month of October with 26 cases and December with 25 cases were the most affected months. (Table 4)

Table 4: Showing distribution of cases according to months

Months	Jan	Feb	March	April	May	June	July	Aug	Sept	Oct	Nov	Dec
Number of cases	22	14	20	19	19	21	23	24	18	26	17	25

Discussion

Females constituting less than males in medicolegal autopsy is a common occurrence and in accordance

to previous studies. [6,7] this can be attributed to the fact that males generally have to move from their homes for their work and often engage in

unhealthy behaviour like alcohol and gambling than women.

Unnatural deaths were more common in the age group in the age group 21-30 and 31-40. This is common across most of the studies. This can be explained by the fact that this is the period where every person is trying to make a living for themselves and hence exposing themselves to various factors and behaviours leading to loss of life like accidents and conflicts.

Road Traffic accidents and hanging were the leading cause of deaths in our study. This is in accordance with most studies which list Road traffic accidents as the most common factor. [7-11]

The high incidence of road traffic accidents can be explained by the location of the study area which is underdeveloped in many areas leading to poor road conditions. Also the use of alcohol in the study population is very high often leading to poor driving judgement on the roads. Medhi GK et al [3] listed that nearly 59% of tea garden workers are prone to alcohol and tobacco use. In our study alcohol use was noted in nearly 30% of these road traffic accidents. Thus socio cultural norms and practices has led to high number of accidents among tea garden workers. However Debata PK et al [12] listed burns as the leading cause of death. This can be explained as the study population was different from our study.

Homicides constituted 5.64% of total cases. This is in accordance with the studies by Panda BK et al [6], Sharma BR et al [7] and Vadysinghe AN et al [10]. However Lim MS et al [8] listed homicide as nearly 30% of cases in platinum mine workers. This difference is due to change in the geographical location.

The increased number of suicide cases noted in the study may be due to low socio economic background of the study population. Also since the study period covered a time when Covid restrictions were in place economic hardship coupled with deteriorating mental health could be a reason for increased number of suicidal deaths. In our study notable inclusion of animal related deaths is due to the fact that these tea garden are in close proximity to wildlife sanctuaries and forests often leading to man animal conflict leading to loss of life. Poisoning cases are common due to easy accessibility to agriculture related pesticides and medicines.

Though monthly variation of cases is not very prominent, increased cases in the month of October, December and January coincides with the festive season in the study area. As a result of social customs and practices, incidences of fights, gambling and alcohol consumption during these months may have led to increased deaths.

The study has a few limitations. We have not done a socioeconomic distribution affecting the manner and cause of death. Also, educational background of the victims were not easily available.

Conclusion

The unnatural deaths among tea garden workers brings forth the fact that socio cultural norms and practices prevalent in the community has led to loss of precious life. Alcohol and subsequent delinquent behaviour has led to increased cases of accidents and fights. Man animal conflicts are on the rise and easy availability of agricultural poisons has led to more suicidal deaths. Behavioural aspects and the findings will give social scientists further research avenues and as such multi organizational research is the need of the hour for this community.

Ethical Approval: Ethical approval has been obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee.

Funding: No funding has been taken for the study.

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